

An Exploration of Teacher's Experiences Towards Managing Challenging Behaviour Exhibited by Learners with Dyslexia

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Abstract:- Enns and Lafond (2007, p. 64) stated that dyslexia "includes difficulties with word identification and reading comprehension, with associated difficulties in spelling, writing, and spoken language," whereas Nugent (2008) confirmed that the term remains contentious and that there is no consensus view of what it is. It has been described as a learning disability that "persistently presents challenges in learning to efficiently read" and "mainly impacts the skills needed for correct and fluent word reading and spelling" (Karande, Mahajan & Kulkarni, 2009, p.382). Some professionals believe that dyslexia is a biologically based condition linked to particular neurological dysfunctions because the description of dyslexia specifies that it is a disturbance in one or more of the fundamental psychological processes (Shaywitz, 1998). The goal of this study was exploration of teachers' experiences towards managing challenging behaviour exhibited by learners with dyslexia in inclusive schools. The research objectives for the study were: to investigate the frequency of challenging behaviours among children with dyslexia attending inclusive primary schools; find out strategies the teachers employ to manage challenging behaviours among learners with dyslexia. The study was influenced by the phonological deficit theory. The study used a descriptive survey. The sample size included 30 learners with dyslexia, 60 teachers, and 10 deputy head teachers. A total of one hundred (100) people made up the sample. With the aid of targeted and purposeful random sampling techniques, the sample size was established. Random sampling was used to choose learners to be monitored in inclusive primary schools with learners with dyslexia, whereas purposeful sampling was used to choose deputy head teachers and educators with special needs education training. In contrast to social and disruptive inappropriate behaviours, the study found that academically improper behaviours were most common among students with cognitive disabilities. The importance of group contingencies, peer counselling, guidance and counselling, and group contingencies as successful methods of managing challenging behaviour was emphasised. The study recommends Early diagnosis is crucial since it will benefit these students intellectually and emotionally. Students will understand that their difficulties are acknowledged, comprehended, and known. Also, it will help educators comprehend the root causes of these students' difficulties. Teachers at short-

and long-term remedial schools must use their knowledge and expertise in workshops for educators in inclusive schools.

Keywords:- Exploration, Challenging, Behaviour, Dyslexia.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ Background Information

There are a number of distinct intellectual disabilities, such as dyslexia, dysgraphia, dyscalculia, dyspraxia, and others. Individual students who experience these issues find it difficult to read, write, or grasp mathematics problems (British Dyslexia Association, 2007). Among these challenges, dyslexia is acknowledged as a very common learning challenge in both eastern and western nations of the world, affecting people of all ages, from children to adults (Elbeheri et al., 2006). According to Westwood (2013), teachers of students with learning problems in inclusive settings face a variety of challenges, including difficult classroom behaviour, cultural pressures, increased teaching workload, regulatory requirements they are expected to meet, parental expectations, and a lack of time and resources to support such students (Hussain, 2009).

Although the causes of the neurological abnormalities that may lead to dyslexia are still unknown, inheritance is thought to be a significant determinant, with dyslexia rates being higher among family members (Frith et al., 2011). Nevertheless, Frith et al. (2011) contend that since the existence of the "condition" is essentially unproven, biological theory lacks strong empirical evidence. Any educational program's success is critically dependent on how well it handles challenging behaviours. When teachers and parents view children with SpLD as "behind," "dumb," "lazy," and "inattentive," it negatively affects their difficulties (Riddick, 1996; Gwernan-Jones and Burden, 2010). This may cause a youngster to become withdrawn or exhibit behavioural issues (Afeafe, 2000; Al-Khateeb and Hadidi, 2010).

The recent discoveries in the field of research (phonological, magnocellular, and cerebellar), which have been strongly associated with dyslexia and continue into adulthood, are not taken into account by discrepancy criteria (Morgan and Klein, 2000). Moreover, dyslexics have reading issues that are not "highly tied to IQ" (Snowling, 2006: 2). The reading process has been mastered by

individuals with lower IQs. It would also be challenging to apply it to an adult dyslexic who has completed their education and is capable of reading and writing at a passable level. Adults can learn coping mechanisms, and while they can. The fact that they can read this does not imply that they are dyslexic any longer. Adults in higher education or the workforce may still require support and special accommodations to successfully complete their coursework and perform their jobs. The IDA (2002) defines dyslexia as:

‘Dyslexia is a specific learning disability that is neurological in origin. It is characterised by difficulties with accurate and/or fluent word recognition and by poor spelling and decoding abilities. These difficulties typically result from a deficit in the phonological component of language that is often unexpected in relation to other cognitive abilities and the provision of effective classroom instruction. Secondary consequences may include problems in reading comprehension and reduced reading experience that can impede the growth of vocabulary and background knowledge’.

According to Weinstein (2002), the majority of students respond favourably to a well-run classroom run by a passionate instructor who is eager to comprehend their pupils and adaptable in their approach. As a result, teachers are better equipped to control troublesome behaviours in their classrooms. Teachers who demonstrate a genuine interest in their students and what they study and do are more likely to develop strong, positive relationships with their students. According to the studies so far, teachers who are close to their pupils and who have a positive relationship with them are better able to handle tough behaviours. According to Walker and Whitaker (2004), teachers must reflect on their own personal views and the ideas of others regarding the understanding of challenging behaviours as well as their own perceptions of challenging behaviour. The word "challenging behaviour" is highly contentious and troublesome. The environment in which it occurs and how teachers interpret it determine what constitutes challenging behaviour (Hill & Hawk, 2000).

The benefit to the child is greater the earlier the identification is made. According to Stag (1972, cited in Fawcett and Nicolson, 1995:3), 82% of children identified in grades 1 and 2 are catching up with their chronological age group, as opposed to 46% in grade 3, and that this percentage increases to 88% in grade four. 10% to 15% less in grades 5 to 7. According to Badian (1988, cited in Ott, 1997: 24), "almost 80% of the pupils could be brought up to their usual classroom work when the diagnosis of dyslexia was made in the first two grades of school."

Dyslexia is a disability that is "hidden," not obvious (Riddick et al, 2002: 91). Similar to how Down's syndrome can be "identified," dyslexia has no outward symptoms. Despite the saying that you should not judge a book by its cover, people with dyslexia, such have been called foolish or lazy because of the blunders they may have committed, as previously said. What about whatever skills they may

possess, such as their capacity for original thought and expression?

➤ *Problem Statement*

Practitioners, educational researchers, parents, and other stakeholders in education from throughout the world have expressed increased worry about students' academic performance in schools. In other words, factors impacting teachers' experience in management of learners' challenging behaviour have an impact on the results of the learners. Teachers have a crucial part in the management of challenging behaviours of the learners. Teachers still struggle with the realities of classroom management challenges despite recent trends in teacher education programs to boost training in this area and in schools to address teachers' weaknesses in classroom management abilities. Moreover, struggling with reading could result in poor behaviour, anxiousness, and a lack of drive (Carnine et al., 1997). Also, it might lead to academic failure in the classroom, which would compromise school achievement academically. Furthermore, experts claim that there hasn't been much research on how teachers manage dyslexic students and how these experiences affect dyslexic students. (Burden, 2005; Burden & Burdett, 2007; Nugent, 2008). According to Claassens (2007), the primary focus of the educational system has been on the academic challenges that these students, as reported by others, face. This research focused on managing challenging behaviour of learners with dyslexia in inclusive settings using alternative intervention strategies as opposed to advice and counselling. No Kenyan research could be found that has focused on bridging the gap on teachers' experience towards managing challenging behaviours exhibited by learners with dyslexia. In light of the aforementioned, this study looked into how teachers manage challenging behaviour exhibited by learners with dyslexia and offered potential remedies.

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

- To investigate the frequency of challenging behaviours among children with dyslexia attending inclusive primary schools.
- To find out strategies the teachers employ to manage challenging behaviours among children with dyslexia.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Neuropathologist Dr. Samuel Orton first publicly expressed his belief that children with reading impairments did not have a low or faulty intelligence in his first article, which he submitted to the American Neurological Association in 1925. (Anderson & Meier-Hedde, 2001). The term dyslexia didn't start to be widely used until the middle of the 1930s, and even then there were many arguments about it. The Greek word combines the suffix *lexia*, which means language, with the prefix *dys*, which means lack (Burden & Burdett, 2007). Hence, the literal meaning is "lack of language" or "difficulty with words." Some people see it as an educational issue, while others see it as a health issue.

In an ideal world, students would arrive at school prepared to learn, with the capacity to follow directions, engage with others in a prosocial way, control their anger, and respect for physical limits (Givner, Lane & Pierson, 2004). Both educators and students with dyslexia may find it difficult to teach and acquire certain concepts. According to Long, MacBlain, and MacBlain (2007), a more thorough investigation of educator learner empathy is required when looking at the effectiveness of the learning environment. When working with dyslexic students, teachers must exercise a great degree of patience and understanding because "things that are supposedly taught one day sometimes have to be relearned the next day" (Rogers, 1991, p.121). Small classes are therefore preferable and therefore doable.

According to a previous study by Levin and Nolan (1996:161), improper behaviour refers to student actions that prevent the teacher from achieving her objectives. In their study, they found that students with cognitive difficulties frequently exhibit inappropriate behaviours that present a challenge to teachers. These behaviours include talking out of turn, calling names, humming while calling out, being off task (daydreaming, fidgeting, doodling, tardiness, inattention), moving around the classroom in an unintentionally disruptive manner (wandering, visiting other students, passing notes, sitting on the desk, throwing objects around the classroom), and showing disrespect (verbal aggression, teasing, pinching, neglecting academic work, refusing to follow directions and assault). In a study with comparable objectives, Brown and Payne (1998) in Virginia, USA, found that students with dyslexia frequently engaged in inappropriate behaviour, including incomplete assignments, absences from class, cheating, and disruptive episodes. There is some degree of these typical inappropriate behaviours in every classroom.

A study was carried out in Kansas secondary schools by Scaggs (2009). The goal of the study was to investigate how youths with modest cognitive disabilities behave delinquently by looking at their pragmatic ties to the school. A descriptive survey was utilized as the methodology. Zero-order correlations and multivariate linear regression were used to analyze the data. The study found that kids with modest cognitive difficulties needed motivation to change the appropriate behaviours they displayed.

Researchers Abu-Tineh, Khasamneh, and Khalaileh (2011) examined instructors' self-efficacy and classroom management techniques in inclusive classrooms with students who had modest cognitive disabilities. The study was qualitative in nature and used a survey design to carry it out. The major statistical method was the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient. According to the study, teachers have historically employed different teaching strategies, such as group contingencies, to engage students with dyslexia. In a later study with related goals, Hackett (2011) found that teachers in a Trinidad and Tobago educational district boasted of the effectiveness of positive reinforcement, including rewards, hugs, praises, and

straightforward guidance and counselling, as strategies for changing the behaviour of learners with dyslexia.

A study was carried out in Pittsburgh schools by Castle (2011). The primary goal of the study was to investigate the relationship between classroom misbehaviour and kindergarten through third-grade math and reading abilities of children with dyslexia. Teachers participated in the survey as responders. The study found that students with mild cognitive disabilities who frequently misbehaved in class as a result of the manifestation of their cognitive level of functioning, which the child constantly experiences, and who were frequently difficult to manage, spent less time in class than students who misbehaved only occasionally. This action forced the classroom rules and regulations to be modified and clarified by the teachers.

➤ *Phonological Deficit Theory*

The phonological deficiency theory has gained a lot of popularity in recent years. This theory is founded on the idea that individuals with dyslexia, regardless of intelligence level (Stanovitch and Siegel, 1994 in Snowling, 1998; 2004; 2006) Shaywitz and Shaywitz. The method that "the brain codes" or "represents" the spoken properties of the words" is the main concern of this theory's proponents. Snowling (2000), p. 35. In order for a child to become a proficient reader, phonological skills must be developed by the time they are five years old. If not, the child will struggle to read and pick up new words (Fawcett, 2001). Children who can manage the sounds in words are better readers and make more reading progress than those who have phonological ability deficiencies (Hatcher, 1994; Tijms, 2004).

Reading is "learned and taught," whereas speech is "natural and inherent" (Shaywitz and Shaywitz, 2005: 1301). People must comprehend that words can be divided into smaller units and that letters represent the sounds of spoken language in order to learn to read (phonemes). A skilled reader can divide a written word into segments and then link each letter to its corresponding sound. Word parts (onset and rime) and individual sounds can be recognized using phonological abilities (phonemes). Include the capacity to recognize a sound (phoneme) and translate it into the letter that represents it (grapheme). Children with dyslexia struggle to identify, manipulate, and code the sounds in words (Doyle, 2002; Shaywitz and Shaywitz, 2005).

Lack of or issues with the aforementioned abilities can lead to issues with naming, non-word repetition, phonological learning, and verbal short memory (Snowling, 2004). Evidence suggests that people with dyslexia struggle with short-term memory, which causes them to retain fewer verbal objects than people without the disorder their age (Snowling, 2004, 2000). Short-term memory stores spoken information as a speech code (Snowling, 2000). According to Conrad's research from 1964, people tend to make more errors when the letters sound alike (b, c, p, t, and v) than when they sound different (f, m, n, s, and x) (Snowling, 2000; Miles and Miles, 1999). This implies that "when a

stimulus is shown visually, what is memorised is its phonological representation" (Miles and Miles, 1999: 41). It appears that dyslexics are limited in the quantity of verbal objects they can store in memory due to a deficiency in phonological coding. Dyslexics unquestionably have issues with their phonological representations, which limits their reading comprehension. Teachers can aid students in becoming more adept readers by assisting them in developing their phonological skills.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study's employed descriptive survey design. According to White (2005), a descriptive design is used to gather pertinent and accurate data for the current study and, when appropriate, make reliable conclusions from the information obtained. In order to choose inclusive schools in Mombasa, Kenya, the researcher used a purposive sampling strategy. The staff at EARC provided support with this. In order to ensure that proper behaviour is instilled in schools, it is likely that purposeful sampling was also employed to choose deputy head teachers in inclusive primary schools.

Selecting schools with inclusive settings was done using a purposeful sample method. Additionally, teachers with three (3) years of experience working with dyslexic learners and in-service training in special needs education were chosen through a purposeful sampling process. Dyslexic learners were chosen by simple random sampling for observation in the inclusive schools.

➤ *Study Participants, Sampling Criteria and Sample Size*

Ten (10) inclusive primary schools with students who have dyslexia were present. Ten (10) deputy head teachers were therefore chosen for the study. The researcher chose six (6) teachers who had had SNE in-service training and had spent the previous three (3) years working with students who had cognitive disabilities. There were 60 teachers in total for the study because there were ten (10) inclusive schools. The researcher chose three (3) learners from each of the ten (10) inclusive schools with dyslexia who had attended for at least three (3) years using a simple random sampling method. The sample included thirty (30) learners, sixty (60) instructors, and ten (10) deputy head teachers.

Table 1 Sample Matrix of Population

Description	Population(N) Regular Schools	Inclusive Primary Schools	Sample size (n)	
			Inclusive primary schools having pupils with mild cognitive disability	Sample size (n) Number of pupils to be observed
Schools	20	15	10	3
Deputy Head teachers	20	15	10	0
Teachers	336	256	60	
Total	356	271	70	30

➤ *Data Storage Analysis and Interpretation*

Data collected for this study were scored, revised, and coded before being entered into Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 for analysis. Statistical measures, including measures of central tendency and dispersion, were used to analyse quantitative data. Therefore, to analyse this data, simple descriptive statistics like frequency counts, averages, and percentages were used. Tables showing frequency distribution, bar graphs, and pie charts were then used to present the results. Qualitative data include detailed descriptions and explanations that show how events occurred chronologically and frequently produce unexpected results (Gray, 2004). Therefore, based on an analysis of the meaning and implications derived from the information provided by respondents and the data that was captured, qualitative data was analysed qualitatively using content analysis.

➤ *Ethical Approval*

Written informed consent was obtained from the participants. It was emphasised that participation in the study was voluntary and there were no subsequent consequences for refusal or withdrawal. The participants were assured that the information they gave would not be made available to anyone. Plagiarism was avoided by acknowledging all sources of information solicited from various researchers and authors. In reporting of research findings, the researcher made sure not to omit any important

information provided by the respondents nor falsify the participants' information to suit the researcher's opinion or pre-empted outcome.

➤ *Study Results*

The study's findings section lists the difficult behaviours that dyslexic students display. This section has also covered the methods teachers use to deal with challenging behaviours.

• *Demographic Information of the Study*

In Mombasa County, Kenya, 60 primary school teachers and seven deputy head teachers from seven inclusive schools provided the data. Results indicate that of the instructor responders, 37 (61.7%) were women and 23, 38.3%, were men. Figure 1 presented the findings.

Fig 1 Teacher Respondents' Gender

The respondent's ages ranged from under 30 to over 60. There were about similar percentages of respondents who were teachers between the ages of 31 and 39 (36.7%) and 40 and 49 (35.0%). The majority of respondents were younger than 30. The results were shown in Figure 2.

Fig 2 Respondents' Age

Based on the survey, only one (1.7% of the teacher respondents) and 27 (45%) of the teacher respondents had teaching experience ranging from 11 to 40. The results were shown in Figure 3

Fig 3 Teaching Experience

Additionally, information was gathered from seven deputy head teachers at seven inclusive schools in Mombasa County. The respondents were given letter tags to maintain their privacy. In Table 2, their distribution was shown.

Table 2 Deputy Head Teachers' Demographic Characteristics

Teacher label	Gender	Qualifications	Administrative experience (yrs)
DHT A	Female	Bachelors	12
DHT B	Female	Bachelors	5
DHT C	Male	Bachelors	7
DHT D	Female	Diploma	9
DHT E	Male	Diploma	10
DHT F	Female	Bachelors	8
DHT G	Male	Bachelors	5

Table 2 findings reveal that there were three male and four female deputy head teachers with an average tenure of eight years and a range of administrative experience of 5 to 12 years. Two (28.1%) held diplomas, whereas five (71.4%) held bachelor's degrees. All of the deputy head teachers also stated that they have received ongoing training on how to deal with students with special needs in inclusive settings. The majority of the deputy head teachers had been in their current schools for at least longer periods of time and had attended in-service training on special needs; as a result, they were more familiar with the management of special needs cases in their schools, and the study conclusions could be based on their information.

IV. FREQUENCY OF CHALLENGING BEHAVIOURS AMONG CHILDREN WITH DYSLEXIA ATTENDING INCLUSIVE PRIMARY SCHOOLS

A. Descriptive Analysis

Disruptive, social, and academic behaviours were used to categorise challenging behaviour. Calculations were made for means, frequencies, and percentages. The findings were shown in Table 3. According to Table 4's findings, all three of these challenging behaviour patterns are quite common. In particular, the academic behaviours of incomplete assignments and trouble recalling newly taught material came in first among reported inappropriate behaviours. Stealing 25 was mentioned the least (41.7%).

Table 3 Prevalence of Challenging Behaviours

Challenging Behaviours						
	Disagree		Undecided		Agree	
	F	%	f	%	f	%
Disruptive behaviours						
Distracting others	3	5.0	1	1.7	56	94.3
Breaking class items	12	19.0	13	21.7	35	58.3
Hyperactive	2	3.4	4	6.7	54	90.0
Social behaviours						
Physical aggression	7	11.6	13	21.7	40	66.7
Stealing	25	46.6	10	16.7	25	41.7
Cheating	19	31.7	10	16.7	31	51.7
Noise making	6	10.0	3	5.0	51	85.0
Difficulty in interaction	13	21.7	7	11.7	40	66.7
Beating others	18	30.0	14	23.3	28	46.7
Academic behaviours						
Assignments incompletion	2	3.3	0	0	58	96.7
Truancy	6	10.0	9	15.0	45	75.0
Difficulty remembering content learned	2	3.4	0	0	58	96.7
Lateness	6	10.0	5	8.3	49	81.7

The researcher also noted how frequently 30 students displayed challenging behaviour. 35 minutes were spent watching the students in a classroom and outside at recess. The means of the behaviours within each category were calculated to determine the average prevalence of each type of behaviour. Results indicate that there are more reports of disruptive behaviour (M = 3.96, SD = 0.61, skewness = -0.72) and academic behaviour (M = 4.18, SD = 0.56, skewness = -2.07). The least amount of social behaviour was observed (M = 3.46, SD = 0.66, skewness = -0.41). The distribution of all three groups was negatively skewed, indicating higher occurrence, which was an intriguing descriptive finding. The results are provided in Table 4.

Table 4 Means, Standard Deviations and Skewness of Inappropriate Behaviours

Inappropriate Behaviours	Inappropriate Behaviours		
	M	SD	Skewness
Social behaviours			
Play engagement	3.27	0.58	-0.09
Fidgets and squirms	3.43	0.50	0.28
Disruptive behaviours			
Interrupt others' conversation	3.37	0.56	-0.07
Distracting during classroom activities	3.60	0.56	-1.04
Hyperactive	3.60	0.49	-0.43
Concentration span	3.53	0.57	-0.73
Touch everything around	3.27	0.78	-0.98
Physically aggressive	2.93	0.69	0.09
Academic behaviours			
Require specialisation programs	2.80	0.71	0.32
Difficulty remembering content	3.60	0.49	-0.43
Difficulty doing class tasks quietly	3.77	0.43	-1.33

According to Table 4's findings, the most frequent challenging behaviour was having trouble working silently ($M = 3.77$, $SD = 0.43$). Hyperactivity ($M = 3.60$, $SD = 0.49$) and being a distraction to others during class activities ($M = 3.60$, $SD = 0.56$) appear to be closely associated with the difficulties of completing class work on a regular basis. Students that needed specialist programs had the least amount of reported inappropriate behaviour ($M = 2.80$, $SD = 0.71$). Only fidgeting, physical aggression, and the need for specialty programs were behaviours that were noticed with reduced occurrences, as shown by the positive skewness values. The scores for all other behaviours were highly skewed in the negative direction.

The study then compiled the report in the behaviour checklist to determine the precise frequency of inappropriate behaviours. To do this, the likert scale (1-4) was divided into two categories: low frequency and high frequency, with the words "never" and "rarely" falling into the former while the words "occasionally" and "often" made up the latter. Table 4.4 gave the results of the study.

Table 5 findings indicate that all of the observed behaviours occur often. However, students who needed specialist programs 11 (36.7%) exhibited the least amount of challenging behaviour.

Table 5 Frequency of Inappropriate Behaviours

Behaviour	Inappropriate Behaviours			
	Low Frequency		High Frequency	
	f	%	f	%
Social behaviours				
Play engagement	2	6.7	28	93.3
Fidgets and squirms	1	3.3	29	96.7
Disruptive behaviours				
Interrupt others' conversation	4	13.3	26	86.6
Distracting during classroom activities	1	3.3	29	96.7
Hyperactive	2	6.7	28	93.3
Concentration span	2	6.7	28	93.3
Touch everything around	4	13.3	26	86.6
Physically aggressive	8	26.7	22	73.3
Academic behaviours				
Require specialisation programs	11	36.7	19	63.3
Difficulty remembering content	1	3.3	29	96.7
Difficulty doing class tasks quietly	1	3.3	29	96.7

B. Qualitative Analysis

Regarding the frequency of inappropriate behaviours among learners with dyslexia, deputy head teachers (DHT) were questioned. It was clear that the vast majority of students had cognition-related learning difficulties that could be remedied. The educable are taking the biggest proportion, according to our %, despite the fact that we have a lot more categories, according to DHT E. The educable, on the other hand, are rare and few in number, and the amount

they can learn from their level of education is constrained, according to DHT F. According to DHT B, these behaviours included truancy, smoking, and theft; according to DHT D, these behaviours included hyperactivity and disruptive behaviour. The behaviours listed by DHT F included "sneaking from school, then incomplete work, pinching others in class, and demonstrating hyperactivity wherever they go, they always want to walk up and down, just to name a few." According to DHT G, the pupils' hyperactivity

and "temper tantrums" posed the largest challenges. Additionally, according to DHT G, students tend to keep to a habit and resist change. He said this:

"Some people find it difficult to switch between activities. They also include those who have obsessions with specific things. He may choose a toy and prefer to play with it exclusively.

Other behaviours mentioned by DHT G included being disorganised in class, having trouble paying attention, and displaying violence that was justified as an attempt to get attention.

➤ *Strategies in Managing Challenging Behaviours of Learners with Dyslexia*

The views of the deputy head teachers were solicited regarding the methods used to address improper behaviours by learners with dyslexia. The research produced a web of methods that included layers of policymaking at the family, school, and community. DHT A, DHT B, DHT C, DHT D, and DHT G all cited guidance and counselling as a crucial tactic. The implementation of a personalised learning technique was crucial in dealing with such learners, according to DHT A and DHT G. In such a program, according to DHT G, it is a multidisciplinary approach where the kid's struggles and abilities are highlighted and a program is made adapted for the child's particular needs so that the training can focus on particular areas that the child may have trouble with.

The utilisation of advisory and counselling clubs as well as life skills groups was also mentioned by DHT B. According to DHT C and DHT G, it was also determined that schools had certain programs in place to handle learners with dyslexia problems, including peer tutoring and the utilisation of resource people. The latter claims that these resource people come from outside the institution. DHT F reported using peer counselling, which entails,.....we group them..... so they can share with and learn from their friends, and we hope that this will result in a change in their behaviour. Then there are group contingencies, where individuals with undesirable behaviours are grouped with those who exhibit positive behaviour. We put them together because we think that if we separate them, the bad ones won't know what is good and won't behave differently.

DHT G supported the comments of DHT F and emphasised the value of support groups. These support groups, in the words of DHT G, "are able to emphasise the issues in each child and they are able to work in tandem in terms of motivating." DHT D said that supervising such learners required offering them little tasks at a time.

V. DISCUSSION

The results of this study showed that disruptive, social, and academic behaviours were negatively skewed, meaning that the majority of respondents indicated that these behaviours were very common among learners with dyslexia. Academic behaviours that included incomplete

assignments, trouble recalling material, and trouble working quietly during classwork duties were the most common of the three. These results corroborate those of Brown and Payne (1998) in Virginia, USA, who claimed that one of the frequent inappropriate behaviours among learners with dyslexia was failing to finish tasks. As a result, it also backs up a study conducted in London in 1996 by Levin and Nolan, who discovered that learners with dyslexia tend to disregard doing academic work. Also, the study discovered that among learners with dyslexia, hyperactivity, lack focus, and disrupting others during class activities were the disruptive behaviours that were most common. This result is consistent with a research conducted in London in 1996 by Levin and Nolan, who discovered that off-task behaviours among learners with dyslexia included fidgeting, inattention, daydreaming, and sketching.

The use of group contingencies, peer counselling, and guidance and counselling, which were endorsed by the majority of deputy head teachers, were important findings of this study on tactics used to manage learners with dyslexia. These results are consistent with those of Abu-Tineh, Khasameh, and Khalaileh (2011) who discovered that different instructional strategies, such as group contingencies, can pique the interest of learners with dyslexia. Therefore, these results are consistent with those of Hackett (2001), who found that teachers in Trinidad and Tobago boasted of the effectiveness of positive reinforcement, including rewards, hugs, praises, and straightforward guidance and counselling, as strategies for altering the behaviour of learners with dyslexia. This survey also discovered that some teachers favoured engaging outside-the-school resource people to counsel students on improving their behaviour. The study also found that some teachers favoured support groups as a method of controlling the improper behaviours of learners with dyslexia. This meant that parents and teachers gathered and spoke about ways to try to change the inappropriate behaviours among the learners with dyslexia.

VI. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to investigate how teachers handle problematic behaviours of dyslexic students who attend inclusive schools and receive long-term remedial education. Gaining knowledge of these students' difficult behaviours and their teachers' management techniques helped educators better understand the implications that dyslexia has on learners' academic school careers. The school seemed to welcome the difficulties brought on by dyslexia. Results showed that a limited number of students were happy at the school and that their teachers did not know much about the difficulties caused by dyslexia. Both the academic and social and emotional needs of the students were satisfied. For schools, teachers, education departments, and ultimately such learners, the contributions of learners to emphasising their educational experiences are vital and warrant more investigation. This study aims to fill a gap in the literature regarding the experiences of dyslexic learners.

➤ *Implications*

Since many parents cannot afford the costs associated with a private diagnosis of dyslexia, there should be more educational psychologists available to schools to aid with dyslexia diagnosis. As a result, many students in traditional classrooms are neither properly diagnosed nor are their difficulties fully comprehended. All educators must prioritise in-service training and workshops because dyslexia is one of the most prevalent learning impairments. It is recommended that research on the understanding, perceptions, and management of dyslexia among educators. It is important to offer positive feedback since it helps learners succeed academically. The administration of the school should encourage student participation in crucial decisions that have an impact on their academic concerns. Also, they must set up lines of communication for all significant players.

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